

Effect of Work Environment on Lecturer's Job Satisfaction and Loyalty: An Empirical Evidence on Private Higher Institution In Banda Aceh, Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of work environment on lecturer's job satisfaction and loyalty. The research sample was 150 lecturers of five private universities (PTS) in Banda Aceh. The questionnaire is the main instrument for data collection. Furthermore, the data were analyzed using a structural equation model (SEM) operationalized with AMOS 21. The study revealed that lecturer work loyalty was positively and significantly affected by job satisfaction and work environment. Therefore, an increase in lecturer work loyalty can be done through university foundation policy intervention in improving the lecturer's job satisfaction and the work environment quality of the university.

Keywords: Job loyalty, Job Satisfaction, work environment, and Structural Equation Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

The existence of tertiary institutions is very important for the development of a country like Indonesia. Educational factors determine the development of developing countries because they affect a number of macroeconomic variables such as economic growth (Amri, 2017), employment opportunities (Amri & Aimon, 2017; Muliadi & Amri, 2019), and even also have an impact on poverty and income inequality in society (Amri & Nazamuddin, 2018; Zulfan & Maulana, 2019). Therefore, the government always tries to encourage the quality of higher education services so that people can get quality education services.

Improving the quality of education in higher education can only be achieved by having qualified lecturers who can support the smooth teaching and learning process well. Besides, the work loyalty of lecturers is also a key factor in organizing the higher education process. Considering the importance of job loyalty, increasing the work loyalty of lecturers is a serious concern for every leader of PTS (Farnita & Amri, 2013).

Theoretically and supported by some empirical research results, one's work loyalty to the institution where they work can be related to job satisfaction and work environment. The relationship between job satisfaction and job loyalty as stated by Wood et al., as cited by Sawitri and Utomo (2012) that job satisfaction increases work loyalty and employee performance. The higher job satisfaction felt by employees, the greater the desire of these employees to work in earnest and ultimately have an impact on their work loyalty. Chen's (2014) research findings also indicate a direct relationship between work loyalty and employee job satisfaction.

In addition to influencing work loyalty, job satisfaction is also affected by the work environment. In general, every lecturer wants a good work environment. The existence of a functional relationship between job satisfaction and work environment as stated by Bakotic and Tomislav (2013) that there is a close relationship between work environment and job satisfaction. The work environment is an important reflection of job satisfaction (Kreitner & Kanicki, 2012). The work environment can not only affect employee job satisfaction but can also affect work loyalty. This is in line with the results of the study of Waqas et al. (2014) also proved that the workplace environment has a significant effect on work loyalty. Employees will tend to maintain their presence in the work environment that they think can provide peace of mind at work. So the better their assessment of the work environment, the higher their loyalty to the work.

Among several PTS in Banda Aceh, there are five PTS that have relatively many students are very much in demand by students, namely Universitas Serambi Mekah, Universitas Abulyatama, Universitas Muhamadiyah Aceh, Universitas Iskandar Muda and Universitas Ubudiyah. The availability of lecturers or permanent teaching staff in each of these tertiary institutions is certainly very important in supporting its operational activities. Therefore, the satisfaction and loyalty of lecturers' work in each tertiary institution are very important to analyze. Initial survey results indicate that job satisfaction and job loyalty of lecturers at each of the tertiary institutions are relatively different from one another. On the one hand, some lecturers have job satisfaction and low job loyalty and on the other hand, there are also lecturers with job satisfaction and relatively high job loyalty. The fact that some lecturers have the desire to move to other tertiary institutions other than the university where they have been teaching indicates that there are serious problems related to job satisfaction and job loyalty.

One of the reasons that are often raised by lecturers so that there is a tendency to change universities is related to work environment factors. Some lecturers have a poor assessment of the ability of tertiary institutions in providing a comfortable work environment for them as teaching staff. Therefore, the question is whether job satisfaction and job loyalty of lecturers are related to their assessment of the work environment in which they teach. Therefore, this study analyzes models of PTS lecturer work loyalty using job satisfaction, rewards and work environment as predictor variables. The use of Structural Equation Modeling as a data analysis tool enables the direction and nature of the relationship between variables to be better known and analyzed in the interests of policy interventions to increase the work loyalty of lecturers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 The link between job satisfaction and job loyalty

Loyalty refers to the desire to protect and save the face of others (Robbins, 2010: 321). The loyalty has a positive relationship with the level of trust. Higher trust, the higher loyalty. The existence of a functional relationship between job satisfaction and job loyalty had been revealed by several previous researchers. Hasan et al. (2013) found that job satisfaction has a direct relationship with employee loyalty. This thing is supported by the research findings of Waqas et al. (2014) that job satisfaction can affect job loyalty. Previously, the research study of Fischer (2010) also found that employee loyalty was related to several factors including job satisfaction. Referring to the empirical literature above, the first hypothesis of this study as follows.

H₁ : The job satisfaction has a positive effect on job loyalty of lecturers.

2.2 The link between work environment and job satisfaction

The work environment can affect job satisfaction and employee work loyalty. In general, every employee wants a good work environment. A better work environment will lead to higher job satisfaction. The assessment of the work environment can have an impact on job satisfaction. Good-perceiving employees in a work environment will tend to maintain their presence in the work environment. In turn, that thing impacts their job loyalty. The existence of the linkage between work environment and job satisfaction is supported by research by Riyanto et al. (2017) which revealed that the work environment had a positive impact on job satisfaction and ultimately affected employee performance. The results of empirical research conducted by Narasuci et al. (2018) with the case of higher education institutions also concluded that job satisfaction was positively and significantly affected by the work environment. When the work environment is perceived well by employees, then these conditions have an impact on increasing job satisfaction. Previously, the results of the study of Bakotic & Tomislav (2013) and Jain & Kaur (2014) also proved a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and work environment. Likewise, Amri's (2014) study supports empirical evidence of the positive impact of the work environment on job satisfaction.

Referring to the empirical literature above, the second hypothesis of this study as follows.

H₂ : The work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction of lecturers.

2.3 The link between work environment and job loyalty

The work environment can affect job satisfaction and employee work loyalty. In general, every employee wants a good work environment. The better the work environment will be the higher the job satisfaction of employees. The employee assessment of the work environment can have an impact on job satisfaction. Employees who have a good perception of their work environment will tend to maintain their presence in the work environment so that the impact on the formation of high work loyalty. This thing consistent with the findings of Ratnawati & Amri (2013) who found that an employee's assessment of the work environment can have an impact on his work behavior in the institutions

where they work. The work environment is not only a physical work environment but also a non-physical work environment such as the supervisor's leadership (Amri, 2015).

The existence of the relationship between work environment and work loyalty empirically has been proven by research findings Soegandhi et al. (2013) that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee work loyalty. The research findings of Waqas et al. (2014) also proved that the workplace environment has a significant effect on work loyalty.

Referring to the empirical literature above, the third hypothesis of this study as follows.

H₃: The work environment has a positive effect on job loyalty of lecturers.

III. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

This study operationalized three variables consisting of job loyalty, job satisfaction and work environment. Job loyalty and job satisfaction are endogenous variables. While, the work environment is exogenous variables. The relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables is not only supported by theoretical basics but also recommended by most studies as explained previously. Therefore, the research framework of this study as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1
Research Framework

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at five PTS in Banda Aceh City consisting of Universitas Serambi Mekah, Universitas Abulyatama, Universitas Muhamadiyah Aceh, Universitas Iskandar Muda and Universitas Ubudiyah. The object of research is related to the lecturer's job satisfaction and loyalty. The variables used to predict the two endogenous variable is work environment. The study population was all permanent lecturers of the foundation who taught at five PTS as mentioned above. The research sample was limited to only 150 lecturers who were randomly drawn from the private university with a total of 30 lecturer for the respective PTS. This amount is considered to represent the entire population.

Following the previous explanation, this study operationalized the three variables measured, namely job loyalty, job satisfaction, and work environment. The work loyalty of lecturers consists of 5 indicators including not wanting to move to other PTS, willing to work seriously, feeling proud to be a lecturer, willing to ignore personal interests for the advancement of PTS, and the similarity of values held by the lecturer with the values that apply to PTS. The lecturer job satisfaction variable consists of 5 indicators including recognition obtained as a lecturer, attention gained from the foundation, the relationship between the foundation and lecturers, the relationship between fellow lecturers and campus management by the foundation. Work environment variables consist of 5 indicators including involvement, task orientation, work pressure, clarity of roles and responsibilities and physical facility support. Each indicator is described in the form of a positive statement. Then, each statement was given an alternative choice in the form of approval level, which was then given a weight based on a Likert scale with scores ranging from 1-5 (Amri, 2013; Amri et al., 2018). Scoring applies provisions 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree and 5 = strongly agree (Amri & Marwiyati, 2019). The scoring is intended to quantify qualitative data such as job satisfaction, work loyalty and work environment (Amri & Surya, 2013; Iskandar & Amri, 2013). Furthermore, the statistical means used to analyze the influence between variables is a structural equation model (SEM) which is operated through AMOS 21. The analysis model has been familiar used to analyze the causality relationship between variables and at the same time between indicators and variables in perception research (Ghozali, 2011).

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1 The result of confirmatory factor analysis test

In this study, variables or constructs studied consisted of work loyalty, job satisfaction, and work environment. The confirmatory factor analysis is intended to test whether the indicators used to measure each variable can manifest the measured variable. In other words, this CFA analysis is also useful for determining whether a measurement indicator used to measure variables is declared valid or not.

Statistically, an indicator can be expressed as a manifestation of the measured variable if it has a loading factor value > 0.70, a critical ratio (CR) value > 2.00 and a p-value < 0.05 (Ghozali, 2011). When an indicator does not meet these criteria, then the indicator is reduced from the model and then the CFA test is continued at the next stage until all the indicators or manifest variables meet the specified criteria.

The CFA test in this study was carried out in two stages. This is caused in the first stage, there are still indicators that do not meet the requirements, namely the third indicator relating to work loyalty (Loy3) with a loading factor of 0.694. Then the indicator is reduced and the CFA test is continued in the second stage. The results of the first and second stage CFA tests as shown in Table 1.

Table1. The result of confirmatory factor analysis

			First Stage			Second Stage		
			Loading Factor	Critical Ratio	p-value	Loading Factor	Critical Ratio	p-value
LK5	<---	Work_Environment	.822			.823		
LK4	<---	Work_Environment	.812	10.864	***	.810	10.847	***
LK3	<---	Work_Environment	.801	10.664	***	.800	10.663	***
LK2	<---	Work_Environment	.796	10.587	***	.797	10.611	***
LK1	<---	Work_Environment	.724	9.339	***	.725	9.371	***
KK5	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.796			.798		
KK4	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.829	10.859	***	.826	10.825	***
KK3	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.808	10.511	***	.807	10.504	***
KK2	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.740	9.409	***	.742	9.448	***
KK1	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.817	10.656	***	.819	10.711	***
LOY5	<---	Job_Loyalty	.753			.763		
LOY4	<---	Job_Loyalty	.778	9.233	***	.760	8.997	***
LOY3	<---	Job_Loyalty	.672	8.282	***			
LOY2	<---	Job_Loyalty	.777	9.222	***	.780	9.256	***
LOY1	<---	Job_Loyalty	.764	9.052	***	.772	9.157	***

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

*** = 0.001

Based on Table 1 above, it can be seen that all the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) testing criteria have been fulfilled, where all indicators have a loading factor value above 0.70, a critical ratio (CR) value above 2.00 and a p-value below 0.05. This means that the indicators for each variable as shown in the above are indicators that can confirm the variable under study.

5.2 Result of measurement model

In accordance with the framework of the research concept, endogenous variables in this study consisted of two variables including job satisfaction and job loyalty of lecturers. Furthermore, exogenous variables consist of rewards and work environment. The measure of goodness of fit in SEM uses several measurements consisting of X2 or chi-square statistics, GFI (Goodness of Fit Index), AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) TLI (Tucker Lewis Index) and CFI (Comparative Fit Index).

Under the CFA stage, testing of the measurement model is also carried out in two stages. In the first stage of the test, several criteria do not meet the requirements such as chi-square statistics > chi-square tables, probability < 0.05, and

the values of GFI and AGFI are each smaller than 0.90. In contrast, other measures such as TLI, CFI, and RMSEA have been met. For more details about the measurement model of the first and second stages as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The result of measurement model

The stage of Test	Goodness-of-Fit Index	Standard Criterion	Statistic Test Value	Decision
First Stage	χ^2 - Chi-square	$X^2_{hit} < X^2_{tab}$	183.680 > 175.198	Good
	Significance Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,029	Not Good
	GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,905	Good
	AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,869	Not Good
	TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,978	Good
	CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,974	Good
	RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,047	Good
Second Stage	χ^2 - Chi-square	$X^2_{hit} < X^2_{tab}$	89.245 < 155.312	Good
	Significance Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,074	Good
	GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,910	Good
	AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,902	Good
	CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,975	Good
	TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,969	Good
	RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,053	Good

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

Based on Table 2 above it can be seen that in the first stage there are still a number of the goodness of fit criteria that have not been met. This is indicated by the value of X^2 test $> X^2$ table ($183,680 > 175,198$) and a probability value of 0.029 ($< 0,05$), and an AGFI value of 0.869 ($< 0,90$). Furthermore, in the second stage of the test, all the criteria have been met with the calculated X^2 value of 89,245. While the table X^2 value of 155,312 is greater when compared to the calculated X^2 value. In other words, the value of $X^2_{hit} < X^2_{tab}$ ($89,245 < 155,312$). This means that the calculated X^2 statistical value meets the specified criteria, so the model is declared not good. The probability value or p-value of the measurement model in this second stage of 0.067 also meets the specified criteria above 0.05. This means that judging from the p-value, the measurement model results meet the provisions of the goodness of fit index. Furthermore, based on the criteria the GFI value has also fulfilled the requirements which are equal to 0.951 greater than the required value of 0.90. Likewise, the AGFI value of 0.952 is also greater than 0.90. TLI and RMSEA values also meet the requirements, namely 0.973 ($> 0,95$) and 0.042 ($< 0,08$), respectively.

5.3 Result of full structural model

After the test of measurement model, the data is then analyzed through confirmatory factor analysis and it is seen that each indicator can be used to define a latent construct, then the next step in using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) as a data analysis tool is to conduct a structural test of the entire model. In this case, the researcher directly tests the relationship between all variables (constructs) studied by involving all the indicators on each construct. The results of the full structural model that explains the interrelationships among all research variables are shown in Figure 2. Furthermore, the results of the full structural model explain the relationship between the research variables as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: The result of Full Structural Model

Figure 2 above not only shows the estimated coefficient values of each exogenous variable against endogenous variables but also shows the loading factor value of each indicator (manifest variable) for the variable. The estimated coefficient of work environment values for job satisfaction and lecturer loyalty as in Table 3.

Table 3 Path coefficients of each research variable

		Estimate Coefficient	C.R.	P-Value	Hypothesis
Job_Satisfaction	<--- Work_Environment	.343	3.596	***	Accepted
Job_Loyalty	<--- Job_Satisfaction	.665	7.392	***	Accepted
Job_Loyalty	<--- Work_Environment	.347	4.463	***	Accepted

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

*** denotes for the significant at 99% level.

Table 3 above inform that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and job loyalty of lecturers. Besides, job satisfaction also directly affects work loyalty. So that the existence of job satisfaction can be interpreted as an intervening variable between the work environment on the one hand and the work loyalty of lecturers on the other hand. In other words, the effect of the work environment on the work loyalty of lecturers does not only occur directly but also through job satisfaction as an intermediary variable. Based on the table above, the discussion of the influence between variables as represented in the following section.

5.4 Analysis of the effect of job satisfaction on job loyalty

Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the work loyalty of lecturers, shown by the estimated coefficient value of 0.665 with a p-value of 0.001 <0.05. The direct effect of job satisfaction on lecturer job loyalty was 44.22 percent. This means that lecturers with higher job satisfaction tend to have higher job loyalty compared to those who have low job satisfaction. Conversely, when a lecturer has low job satisfaction, then these conditions have an impact on reducing the work loyalty of the lecturer concerned. Thus the relationship between job satisfaction and job loyalty among PTS lecturers is in the same direction or positive. Based on the description above, the first hypothesis (H₁) which states job satisfaction has a positive effect on the work loyalty of lecturers can be accepted.

The existence of a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction on the work loyalty of lecturers, supporting the research results of Hasan et al. (2013) which concluded that job satisfaction has a direct relationship with employee work loyalty. In addition, this finding is also in line with a number of previous empirical studies such as Waqas et al. (2014) who found that job satisfaction can affect job loyalty, the results of a study conducted by Hasan et al. (2013) who found empirical evidence that the better job satisfaction the higher job loyalty. Conversely, a decrease in job satisfaction can also have an impact on reducing job loyalty.

5.5 Analysis of the effect of work environment on job satisfaction

The work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of lecturers, with an estimated coefficient of 0.343 and a p-value of 0.001 <0.05. The direct effect of the work environment on job satisfaction by 11.76 percent. This means that lecturers who have a relatively good assessment of their work environment will have higher job satisfaction compared to those who have a less good assessment of the work environment. The better the work environment, the higher the job satisfaction of lecturers. Conversely, when the work environment is perceived as less good, then these conditions have an impact on decreasing job satisfaction. Referring to the statistical results, the second hypothesis (H₂) which states the work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction of lecturers can be accepted.

5.6 Analysis of the effect of work environment on job loyalty

The work environment also has a positive and significant effect on the work loyalty of lecturers. This is indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.347 and the p-value of 0.001 (<0.05). The direct effect of the work environment on the work loyalty of lecturers is 12.04 percent. Increased lecturers' perceptions of the quality of the work environment significantly impact their work loyalty. This indicates that a good work environment is a determining factor in the intensity of the work loyalty of lecturers at the universities where they work. When their work environment is perceived poorly, then these conditions can adversely affect their work loyalty. Based on the analysis, the third hypothesis (H₃) which states that the work environment has a positive effect on the work loyalty of lecturers is accepted.

This study which proves the existence of a positive and significant influence on the work environment on the work loyalty of lecturers is consistent with the results of previous studies conducted by Soegandhi et al. (2013) that an increase in job satisfaction significantly impacts on increasing employee loyalty. This finding is also in line with the results of an empirical study conducted by Waqas et al. (2014) which also proves that the workplace environment has a significant effect on work loyalty. The positive and significant effect of the work environment on the work loyalty of lecturers supports the results of Bakotic and Tomislav's research (2013) which also concluded that there is a positive and close relationship between the two variables. This finding also reinforces the results of a study conducted by Jain and Kaur (2014) which provides empirical evidence that a good work environment can also increase job satisfaction.

Furthermore, testing the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the causality relationship between the work environment and the work loyalty of lecturers refers to the opinions of Baron and Kenny (1986). The test results indicate that the direct effect of the work environment on the work loyalty of lecturers is significant. Furthermore, the indirect effect of the work environment on the work loyalty of lecturers through job satisfaction is also significant. Thus, the mediating effect arising from job satisfaction is partial mediation. This finding is consistent with the results of Narasuci et al. (2018) who found that job satisfaction also mediates the influence of the work environment on employee satisfaction and performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The work environment has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction of PTS lecturers. The better the assessment of lecturers on the work environment at the college where they work the higher the job satisfaction of lecturers. Thus it can be concluded that the increase in job satisfaction of a lecturer is related to higher education policy interventions concerning providing a work environment for lecturers. The work environment also has a positive and significant effect on the work loyalty of PTS lecturers. The better the assessment of lecturers on the work environment at the college where they work, the higher the work loyalty of lecturers. Conversely, when lecturers have an unfavorable assessment of the work environment, then these conditions have an impact on decreasing their work loyalty. In other words, the work loyalty of lecturers is largely determined by their assessment of the work environment provided by tertiary institutions to support the smooth teaching and learning process at the tertiary institution..

Referring to the conclusions above, the suggestions and recommendations of this study are that the leaders of PTS in Banda Aceh should conduct policy interventions oriented towards improving the working environment of the lecturers in the tertiary environment they lead. Technically, it must be communicated with the higher education foundation as the owner of PTS bearing in mind that the policy towards that matter is usually inseparable from the foundation's goodwill. Operationally, the improvement of the work environment can be done through the provision of better work equipment for each lecturer especially the lecturer workspace and the media supporting teaching and learning activities.

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